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ABSTRACT BOOK

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DRIVERS OF THE COMPOSITION OF ROOT-ASSOCIATED MICROBIAL COMMUNITIES IN GARRIGUE ECOSYSTEM

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Plants dominating garrigue (phryganic) ecosystems of the Mediterranean are exposed to low-soil fertility, seasonal high temperatures and drought-stress. Diversity and structure of root-associated microbial communities of two typical plants were investigated. We aimed to identify ecological drivers that determine community assembly processes of host-associated microbial communities. We hypothesized soil properties, plant taxon and season as major drivers.

The roots, rhizosphere, and adjacent bulk soil of early colonizer *Hyparrhenia hirta* (Poaceae) and climax shrub *Sarcopoterium spinosum* (Rosaceae), both naturally occurring in undisturbed sites nearby bentonite and perlite quarrying complexes in Milos island (Greece), were sampled after the dry (autumn) and the rain (spring) period. Microbial communities were analysed via MiSeq-Illumina 2x300 bp sequencing of PCR-amplified 16S, ITS2 and 18S rDNA marker genes to capture prokaryotic, fungal and protist communities.

Overall, all habitats (roots, rhizosphere, and adjacent bulk soil) were dominated by oligotrophic slow-growing Actinobacteria (e.g. *Thermoleophilum*, *Rubrobacteria*), and spore-forming bacteria (e.g. *Bacilli*). This pattern is even more conspicuous in the endo-root bacterial communities indicating

phylogenetic trait conservatism or simply life cycle commonalities in the bacterial root colonizers of phryganic plants. Fungal microbiome was dominated mostly by Dothideomycetes and Sordariomycetes (Ascomycota), followed by Agaricomycetes (Basidiomycota). Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Glomeromycetes) were present in the bentonite bulk & rhizospheric soil only, and were not present in the endoroot fungal community of both plant species.

NMDS analysis of the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity revealed a partial overlap, in all communities (bacterial, fungal and protist) between the bulk perlite and bentonite soils, suggesting low dispersal limitations. However, a clear divergence leading to separation of all communities investigated in this study, between the perlite and bentonite rhizosphere soils was observed, while it appears that plant taxon possesses a diversifying role in the fungal and protist communities. Biotic (plant host) filtering led to strong convergence in the endo-root microbiomes in samples derived from the two soils. This appears stronger for the climax plant *S. spinosum* compared to *H. hirta*, which is a pioneer plant in garrigue biomes and is exposed to microbial colonization even by local assemblages and stochastic processes forming more promiscuous associations.

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